

Non-hematopoietic erythropoietin-derived peptides for atheroprotection and treatment of cardiovascular diseases

Veronika S. Belyaeva¹, Yulia V. Stepenko¹, Igor I. Lyubimov², Alexandr L. Kulikov¹, Alesia A. Tietze³, Indira S. Kochkarova¹, Olga V. Martynova⁴, Olga N. Pokopeyko⁵, Liliya A. Krupen'kina¹, Andrey S. Nagikh¹, Vladimir M. Pokrovskiy¹, Evgeniy A. Patrakhanov¹, Anastasia V. Belashova¹, Petr R. Lebedev¹, Anastasia V. Gureeva⁶

¹ Department of Pharmacology and Clinical Pharmacology, Belgorod State National Research University, 85 Pobedy St., Belgorod 308015 Russia

² Gurus BioPharm LLC, 42/1 Bolshoi Blvd., Skolkovo, Moscow 143026 Russia

³ University of Gothenburg, 9C Medicine Aregatan St., PO Box 462; Gothenburg, Sweden

⁴ Research Institute of Pharmacology of Living Systems, Belgorod State National University, 85 Pobedy St., Belgorod 308015 Russia

⁵ Sechenov University, 19c1, Bol'shaya Pirogovskaya Str, Moscow 119146 Russia

⁶ Kursk State Medical University, 3 Karl Marx St., Kursk 305041 Russia

Corresponding author: Veronika S. Belyaeva (nika.believa@yandex.ru)

Academic editor: Tatyana Pokrovskaia ♦ **Received** 21 July 2020 ♦ **Accepted** 27 August 2020 ♦ **Published** 30 September 2020

Citation: Belyaeva VS, Stepenko YuV, Lyubimov II, Kulikov AL, Tietze AA, Kochkarova IS, Martynova OV, Pokopeyko ON, Krupen'kina LA, Nagikh AS, Pokrovskiy VM, Patrakhanov EA, Belashova AV, Lebedev PR, Gureeva AV (2020) Non-hematopoietic erythropoietin-derived peptides for atheroprotection and treatment of cardiovascular diseases. *Research Results in Pharmacology* 6(3): 75–86. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rrpharmacology.6.58891>

Abstract

Relevance: Cardiovascular diseases continue to be the leading cause of premature adult death.

Lipid profile and atherogenesis: Dislipidaemia leads to subsequent lipid accumulation and migration of immunocompetent cells into the vessel intima. Macrophages accumulate cholesterol forming foam cells – the morphological substrate of atherosclerosis in its initial stage.

Inflammation and atherogenesis: Pro-inflammatory factors provoke oxidative stress, vascular wall damage and foam cells formation.

Endothelial and mitochondrial dysfunction in the development of atherosclerosis: Endothelial mitochondria are some of the organelles most sensitive to oxidative stress. Damaged mitochondria produce excess superoxide and H₂O₂, which are the main factors of intracellular damage, further increasing endothelial dysfunction.

Short non-hematopoietic erythropoietin-based peptides as innovative atheroprotectors: Research in recent decades has shown that erythropoietin has a high cytoprotective activity, which is mainly associated with exposure to the mitochondrial link and has been confirmed in various experimental models. There is also a short-chain derivative, the 11-amino acid pyroglutamate helix B surface peptide (PHBSP), which selectively binds to the erythropoietin heterodimeric receptor and reproduces its cytoprotective properties. This indicates the promising use of short-chain derivatives of erythropoietin for the treatment and prevention of atherosclerotic vascular injury. In the future, it is planned to study the PHBSP derivatives, the modification of which consists in adding RGD and PGP tripeptides with antiaggregant properties to the original 11-member peptide.

Keywords

Atherosclerosis, cytoprotection, epor/cd131, erythropoietin.

Relevance

The high contribution of cardiovascular pathology to the overall structure of the causes of death and disablement in developed countries calls for in-depth study and improvement of correction methods. At the same time, the main task of research in this area is to find ways to prevent and treat atherosclerotic processes as the main cause of cardiovascular mortality.

Atherosclerotic vascular occlusion, as well as thrombosis and embolism following plaque rupture, lead to partial or complete ischaemisation of the affected basin, the clinical consequences of which depend on the localisation and calibre of the vessel. The most significant from an epidemiological point of view is coronary and cerebral vascular lesions, leading to such nosologies as coronary heart disease (CHD) and ischemic stroke (Herrington et al. 2016).

Since the middle of the 20th century, most high-income countries have experienced a sharp decline in mortality due to CHD and brain stroke. For example, in the United Kingdom, cardiovascular mortality rates for middle-aged men (35-69 years old) fell from around 700 per 100,000 per year in 1950 to <200 by 2010, and for middle-aged women from ≈450 in 1950 to <100 by 2010. Most low- and middle-income countries have also reported a decline in stroke-related deaths over the past few decades. However, trends in CHD mortality in these regions have been less consistent: some countries have reported a decline, while others have reported an increase (especially in some Eastern European and Asian countries) in CHD mortality (Bennett et al. 2014; Moran et al. 2014).

The Global Burden of Disease 2010 Study showed that overall, global age-standardized death rates for both CHD and stroke decreased between 1990 and 2010, with a much higher rate in developed countries than in developing countries (GBD 2013 Mortality and Causes of Death Collaborators 2015). Nevertheless, despite relatively reassuring trends, CHD and ischaemic stroke remain the leading causes of premature adult mortality worldwide, indicating the highest importance of research into the underlying atherosclerotic process.

Lipid profile and atherogenesis

The introduction of effective methods for preventing and correcting the atherosclerotic process directly depends on a multi-level understanding of the pathophysiology of the vessel wall lesion. Molecular-biological, instrumental and other research methods provide consistent information on new aspects of the progression of atherosclerosis and

its clinical complications. These advances have not only deepened the understanding of the details of atherogenesis, but have also led to the discovery of many unexpected facts that have called into question many previously dominant concepts, and allowed the development of new therapeutic approaches to combat cardiovascular disease (Libby et al. 2016).

It is now known that the initial event in the development of atherosclerosis is endothelial damage. Endothelial dysfunction (ED) causes infiltration and accumulation of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL) in the sub-endothelial space. In the pathological conditions, LDLs can interact with ROS to form oxidized LDL (oxLDLs) (Ketelhuth and Hansson 2011). Modified lipoprotein particles increase the expression of cell adhesion molecules (VCAM-1, P, and E-selectin) in endothelial cells, resulting in the recruitment of white blood cells (mainly monocytes and T-lymphocytes) into the subendothelial space. These inflammatory cells migrate into the intima during the interaction of protein-chemoattractants, such as of monocyte MCP-1, eotaxin, and interferon- γ . Monocytes are differentiated into macrophages, express scavenger receptors CD36, SRA, and LOX-1 and internalize modified lipoproteins. Due to their appearance, macrophages loaded with lipids are called foam cells, and their presence in the arterial wall is a sign of an early atherosclerotic lesion. T-lymphocytes and mast cells that migrate to the intima, along with the foam cells, secrete a wide profile of cytokines, which contribute to inflammation and the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROSs). The growth factors released by these cells and ROSs stimulate the migration of smooth muscle cells and collagen deposition, which leads to the development of atheromatous plaque (Kattoor et al. 2017).

In 1912, at a meeting of the Society of Russian Physicians in St. Petersburg, a major Russian scientist, N.N. Anitschkow, whose name is now used for the prize for the most outstanding research in the field of atherosclerosis, together with S.S. Khalatov, presented the first results of his revolutionary research to identify the relationship between nutritional factors, blood cholesterol levels, and atherosclerosis.

The main environmental factors determining blood cholesterol concentration are the consumption of saturated and polyunsaturated fats as well as cholesterol in food (Keys et al. 1957; Hegsted et al. 1993; Clarke et al. 1997), although metabolic, genetic and other factors also influence cholesterol levels (Dattilo and Kris-Etherton 1992). The geographical prevalence of atherosclerosis-associated diseases demonstrates their high dependence on national diets around the world. Atheroprotective diets associated with a lower cardiovascular risk have been identified

separately (Mozaffarian et al. 2011). Blood cholesterol (in particular, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol) is a widely recognised risk factor for CHD, as confirmed by a large number of prospective observational studies from around the world (Lewington et al. 2007; Baigent et al. 2010).

During the initial phase of atherosclerosis, the process of fat infiltration of the vascular wall (fatty streak stage) is initiated. Macrophages absorb apoB-containing lipoproteins, which break down in lysosomes, whereas excess free cholesterol enters the endoplasmic reticulum and is esterified by a cholesterol enzyme – cholesterol acyltransferase. The resulting cholesterol ether is packaged in cytoplasmic lipid droplets, which are characteristic of foam cells (Brown et al. 1979; Brown and Goldstein 1983; Rogacev et al. 2012). The chemical modification of ApoB lipoproteins in the form of oxidation and glycation enhances their absorption through a number of receptors (CD36, scavenger receptors and a family of lectin-like receptors) that are not affected by negative feedback from excess cholesterol (Moore and Freeman 2006; Younis et al. 2008; Polonikov et al. 2017). Enzyme-mediated ApoE lipoprotein aggregation increases lipid absorption through phagocytosis (Torzewski et al. 2004; Torzewski and Lackner 2006), while native lipoprotein residues can stimulate the formation of foam cells through the ApoE receptor family (LRP1 and VLDLR) (Fujioka et al. 1998; Schwartz and Reaven 2012). Native LDL uptake through liquid-phase pinocytosis may also stimulate the formation of foam cells (Anzinger et al. 2012; Kruth 2013).

In addition to atherogenic lipoproteins, there are also atheroprotective ones, which are responsible for transporting cholesterol away from the vascular wall, thus reducing its lipid infiltration. The greatest importance was demonstrated for the ApoA-I and HDL proteins that transport cholesterol to the liver. In addition to ApoA-I and HDLs, ApoE production by macrophages is crucial in preventing the formation of atherosclerotic lesions. Most ApoE in plasma is produced by the liver, but about 5-10% is synthesized by macrophages (Linton et al. 1998). ApoE serves as a ligand for hepatic capture and clearance of all the lipoproteins in the ApoB group, except LDLs. Knocking out the ApoE gene in mice leads to hypercholesterolemia and spontaneous development of an atherosclerotic lesion (Zhang et al. 1992; Plump et al. 1992). Therefore, ApoE-deficient mice are some of the most routine models for studying the mechanisms of development of atherosclerotic lesions. In studying the role of macrophage ApoE in lipoprotein metabolism, its crucial role in lipoprotein metabolism between the vascular wall and blood was demonstrated, making ApoE one of the most important targets for atherosclerotic treatment. Interestingly, the atheroprotective effect of ApoE is implemented through several mechanisms. First, the expression of ApoE by hematopoietic stem cells reduces the proliferation and infiltration of monocytes into the intima (Murphy et al. 2011). In addition, ApoE reduces lysosomal accumulation of cholesterol by increasing lipase expression (Wu et al. 2007). It is important that

ApoE secretion by macrophages stimulates outflow in the absence and presence of exogenous acceptors, including HDLs and ApoA-I, which do not contain lipids (Mazzone and Reardon 1994; Langer et al. 2000; Huang and Mazzone 2002). Recent studies have shown that macrophagic ApoE facilitates the reverse transport of cholesterol *in vivo* (Zanotti et al. 2011). It also stimulates the outflow of phospholipids and cholesterol through ABCA1, ABCG1, and SR-BI (Chroni et al. 2005; Yancey et al. 2007a; Kim et al. 2007; Lammers et al. 2009). In addition to cholesterol outflow, macrophage ApoE prevents inflammation (Yu et al. 2004; Ali et al. 2005; Jofre-Monseny et al. 2007; Li et al. 2015) and oxidative stress (Miyata and Smith 1996; Maor et al. 2000; Rosenblat et al. 2002; Rosenblat and Aviram 2002). Local ApoE production is likely to be a critical atheroprotective mechanism, given that the content of atherosclerotic plaques has limited access to ApoA-I and HDLs dissolved in plasma (Fazio et al. 1997; Fazio et al. 2002). Three common polymorphisms of ApoE have been identified in the human population, which are of predictor value in assessing the risk of CHD regardless of plasma cholesterol levels (Davignon et al. 1988). ApoE3 is the most common isoform and is functionally similar to mouse ApoE. In contrast to isoforms ApoE3 and ApoE2, ApoE4 isoform is incapable of either stimulating cholesterol outflow (Cullen et al. 1998; Gong et al. 2002; Okoro et al. 2012) or preventing inflammatory and oxidative activation (Rosenblat and Aviram 2002; Yu et al. 2004; Huebbe et al. 2010). The dysfunction of ApoE4 in the host leads to an increased risk of CHD compared to people expressing ApoE3 or ApoE2 (heterozygotes) (Utermann et al. 1984; Davignon et al. 1988; Song et al. 2004).

Thus, the experience gained from N.N. Anichkov's first work demonstrates that in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis, correlated (environmental) factors must be considered inextricably linked with genetic predisposition (Zárate et al. 2016). This fact leads to a high proportion of research on cardiovascular diseases in the Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) programme and the introduction of the found associations in the early genetic diagnosis panel. The emergence of GWAS and Mendelian randomization analysis opened a new era in the study of the pathobiology of atherosclerosis. Modern genetics has confirmed the causal role of LDLs in atherogenesis, but has also identified new targets that could revolutionize the treatment of the atherosclerotic process.

Inflammation and atherogenesis

Activation of pro-inflammatory cascades in macrophages and endothelium is an essential link in atherogenesis. Activated macrophages are prone to an increased generation of reactive oxygen species, increased cholesterol capture and cytokine/chemokine secretion, resulting in greater LDL oxidation, endothelial cell activation, monocyte recruitment, and foam cell formation (Brand et al.

1993; Wang et al. 2002; Bolick et al. 2009; Adamson and Leitinger 2011; Colin et al. 2014; Peled and Fisher 2014). Oxidative stress, modified lipoproteins and other factors (bioactive lipids, molecular patterns associated with damage, cytokines) stimulate inflammation through their own receptors (Adamson and Leitinger 2011; Chinetti-Gbaguidi and Staels 2011; Colin et al. 2014). In addition, plasma membrane cholesterol in foam cells increases the transmission of signals through inflammatory receptors (Ye et al. 2011; Tall and Yvan-Charvet 2015). The atherogenic role of IL-1 β - and IL-18-mediated inflammatory activation has recently been confirmed (Düewell et al. 2010; Lu and Kakkar 2014); the clinical study has shown that subjects receiving a monoclonal antibody to IL-1 β , kanakinumab, had a significantly lower frequency of repeated cardiovascular events, which did not depend on cholesterol reduction (Ridker et al. 2018).

The formation of macrophage foam cells and transmission of cholesterol-dependent inflammatory signals can be reduced by means of removing cholesterol by atheroprotective HDLs and ApoA-Is using a number of mechanisms, including ABCA1-, ABCG1-, and SR-BI-mediated elimination and water diffusion (Ye et al. 2011; Yancey et al. 2007b; Kellner-Weibel and de la Llera-Moya 2011). In addition, HDLs and ApoA-Is protect against atherosclerosis by reducing inflammation using mechanisms independent of cholesterol outflow (Tang et al. 2009; Kratzer et al. 2014). In addition, small non-coding RNAs have been found to influence the development of atherosclerosis by regulating inflammation and/or homeostasis of cholesterol in different types of cells in lesion foci (Michell and Vickers 2016; Donaldson et al. 2018). MiR-33a and MiR-33b contribute to atherosclerosis by disrupting cholesterol outflow and promoting inflammatory macrophage conversion (Rayner et al. 2011; Horie et al. 2012; Nishino et al. 2018). Other microRNAs, including MiR-223 and MiR-93, have an atheroprotective effect by increasing cholesterol outflow and facilitating the conversion of macrophage phenotype into anti-inflammatory M2 (Donaldson et al. 2018; Zhuang et al. 2012; Vickers et al. 2014; Ganta et al. 2017).

Endothelial and mitochondrial dysfunction in the development of atherosclerosis

Currently, studying the pathobiological processes occurring in endothelial cells in atherosclerosis has led to the understanding that one of the most significant factors in atherogenesis is mitochondrial dysfunction. Mitochondria are a cell metabolic centre that synthesises the cell's main energy currency, adenosine 5'-triphosphate (ATP), through an oxidative phosphorylation reaction. However, the role of mitochondria in eukaryotic cells goes beyond their ability to act as metabolic mediators. These cellular organelles regulate various cellular processes, including

proliferation (Mitra et al. 2009), an immune response (Zhou et al. 2011a), apoptotic cell death (Kroemer et al. 2007), and also participate in the transmission of intracellular signals to the nucleus (Al-Mehdi et al. 2012). Cells in mitochondria vessels are involved in the regulation of a wide range of biological processes. Transgenic mice devoid of a number of mitochondrial proteins usually die during embryogenesis, which coincides with the development of the cardiovascular system, or are prone to the development of a cardiovascular pathology (Miller et al. 2010; Shenouda et al. 2011; Dong et al. 2013; Kröllerschön et al. 2013).

Direct contact between endothelial cells and the bloodstream means that they are particularly vulnerable to damage from molecules circulating in the blood, on the one hand, and that they play an essential "protective" role, on the other hand. ED is associated with the development of almost all vascular diseases. Compared to cells of other types with higher energy needs, the content of mitochondria in endotheliocytes is relatively low. In rat endothelials, for example, mitochondria account for 2-6% of cell volume, whereas in hepatocytes and cardiomyocytes – 28% and 32%, respectively (Dromparis and Michelakis 2013; Kluge et al. 2013). The low content of mitochondria in endothelium indicates that mitochondrial-dependent oxidative phosphorylation does not contribute significantly to the energy supply of this tissue. In fact, endotheliocytes receive most of their energy from anaerobic glycolytic glucose metabolism. For example, in cultured endothelial cells, more than 75% of pig aorta ATPs is provided by glycolysis (Culic et al. 1997). Similar data indicate that mitochondria mainly serve as important signaling organelles in endothelial and vascular vessels (Quintero et al. 2006).

A large number of studies show a causal relationship between mitochondrial and endothelial dysfunctions. Phenotypic endotheliocyte dysfunction is highly correlated with mitochondrial biogenesis dysfunction, reduced mitochondrial mass and altered expression of electron transport chain (ETC) components (Ungvari et al. 2008; Dai et al. 2012). Such processes correspond to natural processes occurring in endotheliocytes during aging. Damaged mitochondria produce excess superoxide and H₂O₂, which are the main determinants of cellular aging (Passos et al. 2007).

Mitochondria are an important source of ROSs and at the same time have an antioxidant function. Although the majority of electrons passing through the redox gradient of the ETC eventually reach the V complex, 1-3% of electrons react prematurely with oxygen in complexes I and III to form superoxide and other types of ROSs known as mROSs (Quintero et al. 2006). Mitochondrial ROSs (mROSs) play a signal role in initiating cellular responses to stress. Changing transmembrane potential is an important factor that triggers excess mROS production under pathological conditions, including hypercholesterolemia, hyperglycemia, smoking, infections, and hypoxia. In ad-

dition to complexes I and III, other sources of mROSs have been identified in endotheliocytes. One of them is NADPH oxidase 4 (Nox4) (Lassègue et al. 2012).

Factors that modulate the production of endothelial mROSs have been proved to participate in atherosclerosis. One of such examples is a protein adapter, p66Shc. The fact that the expression of p66Shc may be relevant to the cardiovascular function is evident from the observation that mice knocked out by p66Shc are protected from ROS-dependent age-related ED (Francia et al. 2004), ED caused by hyperglycemia (Zhou et al. 2011b), and alimentary atherosclerosis (Napoli et al. 2003; Martin-Padura et al. 2008).

Thus, according to the modern understanding of the pathogenesis of cardiovascular diseases, mitochondrial dysfunction plays a significant role in the development of atherosclerosis and related complications (Marzetti et al. 2013; Chistiakov et al. 2018). Such changes in endotheliocytes and myocytes of the vessel wall lead to structural and functional disorders, manifested in the progression of atherosclerosis, hypertension and susceptibility to thrombosis (Peng et al. 2019). Dysfunction of mitochondria in other cells, including neurons and cardiomyocytes, leads to a decrease in their resistance to ischaemia, which is manifested in an increase in lethal outcomes against the background of brain stroke, coronary artery occlusion, infarction of kidneys and other organs. The emerging pathogenetic cascade is becoming a relevant target for a pharmacological intervention.

Short erythropoietin-based non-hematopoietic peptides as innovative atheroprotectors

Based on available information on the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis, one approach to treating atherogenesis is to use drugs with cytoprotective and mitochondrial activities. The current arsenal of drugs with a mitochondrial-oriented mechanism of action includes metabolic enhancers (emoxypine and its derivatives, racetams), metabolic regulators (*trimetazidine*, *mildronate*), and antioxidants (Skulachev ions, *SkQ*). Preclinical studies in vitro and in vivo in recent decades have shown that a 34-kDa *erythropoietin* (EPO), an endogenous stimulant of erythropoiesis has a high cytoprotective activity, which is mostly associated with exposure to the mitochondrial link and has been confirmed in experimental models of ischemic and traumatic lesions of virtually all organs, including endothelium, myocardium, and the brain (Qin et al. 2014; Millet et al. 2016; Nekoui and Blaise 2017). These properties make it possible to consider EPO as an agent with a universal cytoprotective orientation. The remote (hematopoiesis) and paracrine action is associated with the ability of EPO to influence the cell cycle and to reduce the pro-apoptotic orientation of cells, but the eryth-

ropoietic action is mediated by the homodimeric receptor complex of the erythropoietin receptor (EPOR/EPOR), while the cytoprotective, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions are mediated by the heterodimeric complex of EPOR/CD131 (Brines et al. 2004).

Despite the promising results of preclinical studies, information about the EPO antiapoptotic activity received by hundreds of research teams is poorly translated into clinical reality. As a result, the search for molecules that selectively mimic the cytoprotective effects of EPO is one of the important tasks of modern pharmacology. To date, compounds with an amino acid sequence identical to that of EPO, but differing in carbohydrate fragment, have become very common. Such modifications improve the pharmacokinetics and reduce the ability to influence hemopoiesis, preserving the tissue-protective activity of the molecule. However, these drugs have not demonstrated high clinical efficacy as cytoprotectors either, possibly due to their low ability to penetrate histogenetic barriers. A principally novel approach is the search for low-molecular peptide derivatives of EPO, which have an antiapoptotic activity and freely penetrate through biological barriers. The first of such derivatives is an 11-amino acid peptide *PHBSP*, which is an amino acid chain "Pyr-Glu-Gln-Leu-Glu-Arg-Ala-Leu-Asn-Ser-Ser" and has a selective affinity for the heterodimeric complex EPOR/CD131 (Brines et al. 2004). In developing this peptide, the authors relied on the amino acid sequence of alpha-spiral B erythropoietin, since this is the only structural part of the molecule that does not participate in the spatial interaction with the homodimeric complex EPOR/EPOR. Several studies have shown that *PHBSP* has more pronounced antiapoptotic properties than the basic molecule, exhibits an analgesic activity and does not have a hemopoietic effect intrinsic to EPO (Brines et al. 2004; Swartjes et al. 2014; Zhang et al. 2017; Yang et al. 2019). However, a significant disadvantage of *PHBSP* is its very short half-life, approaching several minutes. In addition, studies carried out in our laboratory in vivo and in vitro have revealed a pro-thrombotic activity in this peptide, which is to some extent characteristic of all erythropoietin molecules.

Conclusion

In our view, a modification of *PHBSP* to improve the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic parameters may be a further promising development of a short-chain-peptide-based CVD pharmacotherapy. To solve this problem, our team, together with the scientific team of A. Titze (University of Gothenburg), has worked on searching for the ways of modifying the base molecule. To eliminate the pro-thrombotic activity, it was decided to add the amino

acid sequence **RGD** (Arg-Gly-Asp) to PHBSP. It is known that this motif has pronounced antiaggregant properties (Pytela et al. 1986, Sheu et al. 1995, Hung et al. 2017). In parallel, the **PGP** motive (Pro-Gly-Pro) was added to a number of compounds to improve their pharmacokinetic characteristics. This amino acid sequence stabilizes the molecule in biological media by inhibiting the activity of proteolytic enzymes (Shevchenko et al. 2019). Moreover, PGP also has the ability to block the angiotensin-converting enzyme (Wang et al. 2011), one of the most important proatherogenic factors that catalyzes the reaction of angiotensin II formation and promotes vascular wall remodeling (Montezano et al. 2014). A number of Russian studies have also identified the antithrombotic and antiaggregant properties of PGP (Pastorova et al. 2001; Lyapina et al. 2007; Liapina et al. 2010), making its adherence to PHBSP even more promising. The key question remains the nature of embedding RGD and PGP motifs in the base molecule. A bioinformatic analysis has made it possible

to determine the most optimal localizations for joining tripeptides, which do not affect the pharmacophores of interest, preserving both cytoprotective (Korokin et al. 2019; Korokin et al. 2020) and antiaggregant activities. Further in vitro and in vivo studies will open up the possibility of screening the most promising compounds.

Acknowledgements

The reported work was funded by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation (Agreement No. 05.605.21.0191, unique Agreement id – RFMEFI60519X0191).

Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

References

- Adamson S, Leitinger N (2011) Phenotypic modulation of macrophages in response to plaque lipids. *Current Opinion in Lipidology* 22(5): 335–342. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MOL.0b013e32834a97e4> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Ali K, Middleton M, Puré E, Rader DJ (2005) Apolipoprotein E suppresses the type I inflammatory response in vivo. *Circulation Research* 97(9): 922–927. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.RES.0000187467.67684.43> [PubMed]
- Al-Mehdi AB, Pastukh VM, Swiger BM, Reed DJ, Patel MR, Bardwell GC (2012) Perinuclear mitochondrial clustering creates an oxidant-rich nuclear domain required for hypoxia-induced transcription. *Science Signaling* 5(231): ra47. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scisignal.2002712> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Anzinger JJ, Chang J, Xu Q, Barthwal MK, Bohnacker T, Wymann MP, Kruth HS (2012) Murine bone marrow-derived macrophages differentiated with GM-CSF become foam cells by PI3K γ -dependent fluid-phase pinocytosis of native LDL. *Journal of Lipid Research* 53(1): 34–42. <https://doi.org/10.1194/jlr.M018887> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Bennett DA, Krishnamurthi RV, Barker-Collo S, Forouzanfar MH, Naghavi M, Connor M, Lawes CM, Moran AE, Anderson LM, Roth GA, Mensah GA, Ezzati M, Murray CJ, Feigin VL (2014) Global burden of diseases, injuries, and risk factors 2010 Study Stroke Expert Group. The global burden of ischemic stroke: findings of the GBD 2010 study. *Global Heart* 9: 107–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ghheart.2014.01.001> [PubMed]
- Bolick DT, Skaffen MD, Johnson LE, Kwon SC, Howatt D, Daugherty A, Ravichandran KS, Hedrick CC (2009) G2A deficiency in mice promotes macrophage activation and atherosclerosis. *Circulation Research* 104(3): 318–327. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.108.181131> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Brand K, Mackman N, Curtiss LK (1993) Interferon-gamma inhibits macrophage apolipoprotein E production by posttranslational mechanisms. *The Journal of Clinical Investigation* 91(5): 2031–2039. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI116425> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Brines M, Grasso G, Fiordaliso F, Sfacteria A, Ghezzi P, Fratelli M, Latini R, Xie QW, Smart J, Su-Rick CJ, Pobre E, Diaz D, Gomez D, Hand C, Coleman T, Cerami A (2004) Erythropoietin mediates tissue protection through an erythropoietin and common beta-subunit heteroreceptor. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 101(41): 14907–14912. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0406491101> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Brown MS, Goldstein JL (1983) Lipoprotein metabolism in the macrophage: implications for cholesterol deposition in atherosclerosis. *Annual Review of Biochemistry* 52: 223–261. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.bi.52.070183.001255> [PubMed]
- Brown MS, Goldstein JL, Krieger M, Ho YK, Anderson RG (1979) Reversible accumulation of cholesteryl esters in macrophages incubated with acetylated lipoproteins. *The Journal of Cell Biology* 82(3): 597–613. <https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.82.3.597> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Chinetti-Gbaguidi G, Staels B (2011) Macrophage polarization in metabolic disorders: functions and regulation. *Current Opinion in Lipidology* 22(5): 365–372. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MOL.0b013e32834a77b4> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Chistiakov DA, Shkurat TP, Melnichenko AA, Grechko AV, Orekhov AN (2018) The role of mitochondrial dysfunction in cardiovascular disease: A brief review. *Annals of Medicine* 50(2): 121–127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07853890.2017.1417631> [PubMed]
- Cholesterol Treatment Trialists' (CTT) Collaboration, Baigent C, Blackwell L, Emberson J, Holland L. E, Reith C, Bhala N, Peto R, Barnes EH, Keech A, Simes J, Collins R (2010) Efficacy and safety of more intensive lowering of LDL cholesterol: a meta-analysis of data from 170,000 participants in 26 randomised trials. *Lancet* 376(9753): 1670–1681. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(10\)61350-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(10)61350-5) [PubMed] [PMC]
- Chroni A, Nieland TJ, Kypreos KE, Krieger M, Zannis VI (2005) SR-BI mediates cholesterol efflux via its interactions with lipid-bound ApoE. Structural mutations in SR-BI diminish cholesterol

- efflux. *Biochemistry* 44(39): 13132–13143. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bi051029o> [PubMed]
- Clarke R, Frost C, Collins R, Appleby P, Peto R (1997) Dietary lipids and blood cholesterol: quantitative meta-analysis of metabolic ward studies. *BMJ* 314(7074): 112–117. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.314.7074.112> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Colin S, Chinetti-Gbaguidi G, Staels B (2014) Macrophage phenotypes in atherosclerosis. *Immunological Reviews* 262(1): 153–166. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imr.12218>
 - Culic O, Gruwel ML, Schrader J (1997) Energy turnover of vascular endothelial cells. *American Journal of Physiology-Cell Physiology* 273(1): 205–213. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpcell.1997.273.1.C205> [PubMed]
 - Cullen P, Cignarella A, Brennhansen B, Mohr S, Assmann G, von Eckardstein A (1998) Phenotype-dependent differences in apolipoprotein E metabolism and in cholesterol homeostasis in human monocyte-derived macrophages. *The Journal of Clinical Investigation* 101(8): 1670–1677. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI119887> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Dai DF, Rabinovitch PS, Ungvari Z (2012) Mitochondria and cardiovascular aging. *Circulation Research* 110(8): 1109–1124. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.111.246140> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Dattilo AM, Kris-Etherton PM (1992) Effects of weight reduction on blood lipids and lipoproteins: a meta-analysis. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* 56(2): 320–328. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/56.2.320> [PubMed]
 - Davignon J, Gregg RE, Sing CF (1988) Apolipoprotein E polymorphism and atherosclerosis. *Arteriosclerosis* 8(1): 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.atv.8.1.1>
 - Donaldson CJ, Lao KH, Zeng L (2018) The salient role of microRNAs in atherogenesis. *Journal of Molecular and Cellular Cardiology* 122: 98–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yjmcc.2018.08.004> [PubMed]
 - Dong M, Yang X, Lim S, Cao Z, Honek J, Lu H (2013) Cold exposure promotes atherosclerotic plaque growth and instability via UCP1-dependent lipolysis. *Cell Metabolism* 18(1): 118–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2013.06.003> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Dromparis P, Michelakis ED (2013) Mitochondria in vascular health and disease. *Annual Review of Physiology* 75: 95–126. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-physiol-030212-183804> [PubMed]
 - Duewell P, Kono H, Rayner KJ, Sirois CM, Vladimer G, Bauernfeind FG, Abela GS, Franchi L, Nuñez G, Schnurr M, Espevik T, Lien E, Fitzgerald KA, Rock KL, Moore KJ, Wright SD, Hornung V, Latz E (2010) NLRP3 inflammasomes are required for atherogenesis and activated by cholesterol crystals. *Nature* 464(7293): 1357–1361. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature08938> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Fazio S, Babaev VR, Burleigh ME, Major AS, Hasty AH, Linton MF (2002) Physiological expression of macrophage apoE in the artery wall reduces atherosclerosis in severely hyperlipidemic mice. *Journal of Lipid Research* 43(10): 1602–1609. <https://doi.org/10.1194/jlr.m200108-jlr200> [PubMed]
 - Fazio S, Babaev VR, Murray AB, Hasty AH, Carter KJ, Gleaves LA, Atkinson JB, Linton MF (1997) Increased atherosclerosis in mice reconstituted with apolipoprotein E null macrophages. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 94(9): 4647–4652. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.94.9.4647> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Francia P, Delli Gatti C, Bachschmid M, Martin-Padura I, Savoia C, Migliaccio E (2004) Deletion of p66shc gene protects against age-related endothelial dysfunction. *Circulation* 110(18): 2889–2895. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.0000147731.24444.4D> [PubMed]
 - Fujioka Y, Cooper AD, Fong LG (1998) Multiple processes are involved in the uptake of chylomicron remnants by mouse peritoneal macrophages. *Journal of Lipid Research* 39(12): 2339–2349. [PubMed]
 - Ganta VC, Choi MH, Kutateladze A, Fox TE, Farber CR, Annex BH (2017) A microRNA93-interferon regulatory factor-9-immunoresponsive hene-1-itaconic acid pathway modulates M2-like macrophage polarization to revascularize ischemic muscle. *Circulation* 135(24): 2403–2425. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.116.025490> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - GBD (2013) Mortality and Causes of Death Collaborators (2015) Global, regional, and national age-sex specific all-cause and cause-specific mortality for 240 causes of death, 1990–2013: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2013. *Lancet* 385(9963): 117–171. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(14\)61682-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(14)61682-2) [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Gong JS, Kobayashi M, Hayashi H, Zou K, Sawamura N, Fujita SC, Yanagisawa K, Michikawa M (2002) Apolipoprotein E (ApoE) isoform-dependent lipid release from astrocytes prepared from human ApoE3 and ApoE4 knock-in mice. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry* 277(33): 29919–29926. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M203934200> [PubMed]
 - Hegsted DM, Ausman LM, Johnson JA, Dallal GE (1993) Dietary fat and serum lipids: an evaluation of the experimental data. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* 57(6): 875–883. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/57.6.875> [PubMed]
 - Herrington W, Lacey B, Sherliker P, Armitage J, Lewington S (2016) Epidemiology of atherosclerosis and the potential to reduce the global burden of atherothrombotic disease. *Circulation Research* 118: 535–546. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.115.307611> [PubMed]
 - Horie T, Baba O, Kuwabara Y, Chujo Y, Watanabe S, Kinoshita M, Horiguchi M, Nakamura T, Chonabayashi K, Hishizawa M, Hasegawa K, Kume N, Yokode M, Kita T, Kimura T, Ono K (2012) MicroRNA-33 deficiency reduces the progression of atherosclerotic plaque in ApoE^{-/-} mice. *Journal of the American Heart Association* 1(6): e003376. <https://doi.org/10.1161/JAHA.112.003376> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Huang ZH, Mazzone T (2002) ApoE-dependent sterol efflux from macrophages is modulated by scavenger receptor class B type I expression. *Journal of Lipid Research* 43(3): 375–382. [PubMed]
 - Huebbe P, Lodge JK, Rimbach G (2010) Implications of apolipoprotein E genotype on inflammation and vitamin E status. *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research* 54(5): 623–630. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.200900398> [PubMed]
 - Hung YC, Kuo YJ, Huang SS, Huang TF (2017) Trimucrin, an Arg-Gly-Asp containing disintegrin, attenuates myocardial ischemia-reperfusion injury in murine by inhibiting platelet function. *European Journal of Pharmacology* 813: 24–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2017.07.039> [PubMed]
 - Jofre-Monseny L, Loboda A, Wagner AE, Huebbe P, Boesch-Saadatmandi C, Jozkiewicz A, Minihane AM, Dulak J, Rimbach G (2007) Effects of apoE genotype on macrophage inflammation and heme oxygenase-1 expression. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications* 357(1): 319–324. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2007.03.150> [PubMed] [PMC]

- Kattoor AJ, Pothineni N, Palagiri D, Mehta JL (2017) Oxidative stress in atherosclerosis. *Current Atherosclerosis Reports* 19(11): 42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11883-017-0678-6> [PubMed]
- Kellner-Weibel G, de la Llera-Moya M (2011) Update on HDL receptors and cellular cholesterol transport. *Current Atherosclerosis Reports* 13(3): 233–241. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11883-011-0169-0> [PubMed]
- Ketelhuth DF, Hansson GK (2011) Cellular immunity, low-density lipoprotein and atherosclerosis: break of tolerance in the artery wall. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis* 106(5): 779–786. <https://doi.org/10.1160/TH11-05-0321> [PubMed]
- Keys A, Anderson JT, Grande F (1957) Prediction of serum-cholesterol responses of man to changes in fats in the diet. *Lancet* 273(7003): 959–966. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(57\)91998-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(57)91998-0) [PubMed]
- Kim WS, Rahmanto AS, Kamili A, Rye KA, Guillemin GJ, Gelissen IC, Jessup W, Hill AF, Garner B (2007) Role of ABCG1 and ABCA1 in regulation of neuronal cholesterol efflux to apolipoprotein E discs and suppression of amyloid-beta peptide generation. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry* 282(5): 2851–2861. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M607831200> [PubMed]
- Kluge MA, Fetterman JL, Vita JA (2013) Mitochondria and endothelial function. *Circulation Research* 112(8): 1171–1188. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.111.300233> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Korokin M, Gureev V, Gudyrev O, Golubev I, Korokina L, Pereyapkina A, Pokrovskaya T, Lazareva G, Soldatov V, Zatolokina M, Pobeda A, Avdeeva E, Beskhnelnitsyna E, Denisjuk T, Avdeeva N, Bushueva O, Pokrovskii M (2020) Erythropoietin mimetic peptide (pHBSP) corrects endothelial dysfunction in a rat model of preeclampsia. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 21(18): E6759. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21186759> [PubMed]
- Korokin M, Soldatov V, Tietze A, Golubev M, Belykh A, Kubekina M, Puchenkova O, Denisjuk T, Gureyev V, Pokrovskaya T, Gudyrev O, Zhuchenko M, Zatolokina M, Pokrovskiy M (2019) 11-amino acid peptide imitating the structure of erythropoietin α -helix b improves endothelial function, but stimulates thrombosis in rats. *Pharmacy & Pharmacology* 7(6): 312–320. <https://doi.org/10.19163/2307-9266-2019-7-6-312-320>
- Kratzer A, Giral H, Landmesser U (2014) High-density lipoproteins as modulators of endothelial cell functions: alterations in patients with coronary artery disease. *Cardiovascular Research* 103(3): 350–361. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cvr/cvu139> [PubMed]
- Kroemer G, Galluzzi L, Brenner C (2007) Mitochondrial membrane permeabilization in cell death. *Physiological Reviews* 87(1): 99–163. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00013.2006> [PubMed]
- Kröll-Schön S, Jansen T, Schüler A, Oelze M, Wenzel P, Hausding M (2013) Proliferator coactivator 1 α deletion induces angiotensin II – associated vascular dysfunction by increasing mitochondrial oxidative stress and vascular inflammation. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology* 33(8): 1928–1935. <https://doi.org/10.1161/ATVBAHA.113.301717> [PubMed]
- Kruth HS (2013) Fluid-phase pinocytosis of LDL by macrophages: a novel target to reduce macrophage cholesterol accumulation in atherosclerotic lesions. *Current Pharmaceutical Design* 19(33): 5865–5872. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1381612811319330005> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Lammers B, Out R, Hildebrand RB, Quinn CM, Williamson D, Hoekstra M, Meurs I, Van Berkel TJ, Jessup W, Van Eck M (2009) Independent protective roles for macrophage Abcg1 and Apoe in the atherosclerotic lesion development. *Atherosclerosis* 205(2): 420–426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2009.01.017> [PubMed]
- Langer C, Huang Y, Cullen P, Wiesenhütter B, Mahley RW, Assmann G, von Eckardstein A (2000) Endogenous apolipoprotein E modulates cholesterol efflux and cholesteryl ester hydrolysis mediated by high-density lipoprotein-3 and lipid-free apolipoproteins in mouse peritoneal macrophages. *Journal of Molecular Medicine* 78(4): 217–227. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s001090000096> [PubMed]
- Lassègue B, Martín AS, Griendling KK (2012) Biochemistry, physiology, and pathophysiology of NADPH oxidases in the cardiovascular. *Circulation Research* 110(10): 1364–1390. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.111.243972> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Li K, Ching D, Luk FS, Raffai RL (2015) Apolipoprotein E enhances microRNA-146a in monocytes and macrophages to suppress nuclear factor- κ B-driven inflammation and atherosclerosis. *Circulation Research* 117(1): e1–e11. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.117.305844> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Liapina LA, Grigor'eva ME, Andreeva LA, Miasoedov NF (2010) Protective antithrombotic effects of proline-containing peptides in the animal body subjected to stress. *Biology Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences* 37(4): 462–467. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1062359010040096> [PubMed]
- Libby P, Bornfeldt KE, Tall AR (2016) Atherosclerosis: successes, surprises, and future challenges. *Circulation Research* 118(4): 531–534. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.116.308334> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Linton MF, Hasty AH, Babaev VR, Fazio S (1998) Hepatic apo E expression is required for remnant lipoprotein clearance in the absence of the low density lipoprotein receptor. *The Journal of Clinical Investigation* 101(8): 1726–1736. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI2181> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Lu X, Kakkar V (2014) Inflammasome and atherogenesis. *Current Pharmaceutical Design* 20(1): 108–124. <https://doi.org/10.2174/13816128113199990586> [PubMed]
- Lyapina LA, Pastorova VE, Obergan TY (2007) Changes in hemostatic parameters after intranasal administration of peptide Pro-Gly-Pro. *Bulleting of Experimental Biology and Medicine* 144(4): 491–493. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10517-007-0358-6>
- Maor I, Kaplan M, Hayek T, Vaya J, Hoffman A, Aviram M (2000) Oxidized monocyte-derived macrophages in aortic atherosclerotic lesion from apolipoprotein E-deficient mice and from human carotid artery contain lipid peroxides and oxysterols. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications* 269(3): 775–780. <https://doi.org/10.1006/bbrc.2000.2359> [PubMed]
- Martin-Padura I, Nigris F, Migliaccio E, Mansueto G, Minardi S, Rienzo M (2008) Deletion confers vascular protection in advanced atherosclerosis in hypercholesterolemic apolipoprotein E knockout mice. *Endothelium* 15(5-6): 276–287. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10623320802487791> [PubMed]
- Marzetti E, Csiszar A, Dutta D, Balagopal G, Calvani R, Leeuwenburgh C (2013) Role of mitochondrial dysfunction and altered autophagy in cardiovascular aging and disease: from mechanisms to therapeutics. *American Journal of Physiology – Heart Circulatory Physiology* 305(4): 459–476. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00936.2012> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Mazzone T, Reardon C (1994) Expression of heterologous human apolipoprotein E by J774 macrophages enhances cholesterol efflux to HDL3. *Journal of Lipid Research* 35(8): 1345–1353. [PubMed]

- Michell DL, Vickers KC (2016) Lipoprotein carriers of microRNAs. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta* 1861(12 Pt B): 2069–2074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbali.2016.01.011> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Miller JD, Peotta VA, Chu Y, Weiss RM, Zimmerman K, Brooks RM (2010) MnSOD protects against COX1-mediated endothelial dysfunction in chronic heart failure. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart Circulatory Physiology* 298(5): 1600–1607. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.01108.2009> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Millet A, Bouzat P, Trouve-Buisson T, Batandier C, Pernet-Gallay K, Gaide-Chevronnay L (2016) Erythropoietin and its derivatives modulate mitochondrial dysfunction after diffuse traumatic brain injury. *Journal of Neurotrauma* 33(17): 1625–1633. <https://doi.org/10.1089/neu.2015.4160> [PubMed]
- Mitra K, Wunder C, Roysam B, Lin G, Lippincott-Schwartz J (2009) A hyperfused mitochondrial state achieved at G1-S regulates cyclin E buildup and entry into S phase. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 106(29): 11960–11965. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0904875106> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Miyata M, Smith JD (1996) Apolipoprotein E allele-specific antioxidant activity and effects on cytotoxicity by oxidative insults and beta-amyloid peptides. *Nature Genetics* 14(1): 55–61. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng0996-55> [PubMed]
- Montezano AC, Nguyen Dinh Cat A, Rios FJ, Touyz RM (2014) Angiotensin II and vascular injury. *Current Hypertension Reports* 16(6): 431. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11906-014-0431-2> [PubMed]
- Moore KJ, Freeman MW (2006) Scavenger receptors in atherosclerosis: beyond lipid uptake. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology* 26(8): 1702–1711. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.ATV.0000229218.97976.43> [PubMed]
- Moran AE, Forouzanfar MH, Roth GA, Mensah GA, Ezzati M, Murray CJ, Naghavi M (2014) Temporal trends in ischemic heart disease mortality in 21 world regions, 1980 to 2010: the Global Burden of Disease 2010 study. *Circulation* 129: 1483–1492. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.113.004042> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Mozaffarian D, Appel LJ, Van Horn L (2011) Components of a cardioprotective diet: new insights. *Circulation* 123(24): 2870–2891. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.110.968735> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Murphy AJ, Akhtari M, Tolani S, Pagler T, Bijl N, Kuo CL, Wang M, Sanson M, Abramowicz S, Welch C, Bochem AE, Kuivenhoven JA, Yvan-Charvet L, Tall AR (2011) ApoE regulates hematopoietic stem cell proliferation, monocytosis, and monocyte accumulation in atherosclerotic lesions in mice. *The Journal of Clinical Investigation* 121(10): 4138–4149. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI57559> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Napoli C, Martin-Padura I, de Nigris F, Giorgio M, Mansueto G, Somma P (2003) Deletion of the p66Shc longevity gene reduces systemic and tissue oxidative stress, vascular cell apoptosis, and early atherogenesis in mice fed a high-fat diet. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 100(4): 2112–2116. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0336359100> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Nekoui A, Blaise G (2017) Erythropoietin and nonhematopoietic effects. *The American Journal of the Medical Sciences* 353(1):76-81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjms.2016.10.009> [PubMed]
- Nishino T, Horie T, Baba O, Sowa N, Hanada R, Kuwabara Y, Nakao T, Nishiga M, Nishi H, Nakashima Y, Nakazeki F, Ide Y, Koyama S, Kimura M, Nagata M, Yoshida K, Takagi Y, Nakamura T, Hasegawa K, Miyamoto S, Kimura T, Ono K (2018) SREBF1/MicroRNA-33b Axis Exhibits Potent Effect on Unstable Atherosclerotic Plaque Formation In Vivo. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology* 38(10): 2460–2473. <https://doi.org/10.1161/ATVBAHA.118.311409> [PubMed]
- Okoro EU, Zhao Y, Guo Z, Zhou L, Lin X, Yang H (2012) Apolipoprotein E4 is deficient in inducing macrophage ABCA1 expression and stimulating the Sp1 signaling pathway. *PLoS one* 7(9): e44430. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0044430> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Passos JF, Saretzki G, Ahmed S, Nelson G, Richter T, Peters H (2007) Mitochondrial dysfunction accounts for the stochastic heterogeneity in telomere-dependent senescence. *PLoS Biology* 5(5): 2889–2895. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.0050110> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Pastorova VE, Liapina LA, Alshmarin IP, Ostrovskaia PU, Gudasheva TA, Lugovskoi EV (2001) Fibrin-depolymerization activity and the antiplatelet effect of small cyclic and linear proline-containing peptides. *Biology Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences* 28(5): 593–596. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1016700412205> [PubMed]
- Peled M, Fisher EA (2014) Dynamic Aspects of Macrophage Polarization during Atherosclerosis Progression and Regression. *Frontiers in Immunology* 5: 579. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2014.00579> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Peng W, Cai G, Xia Y, Chen J, Wu P, Wang Z, Li G, Wei D (2019) Mitochondrial dysfunction in atherosclerosis. *DNA and Cell Biology* 38(7): 597–606. <https://doi.org/10.1089/dna.2018.4552> [PubMed]
- Plump AS, Smith JD, Hayek T, Aalto-Setälä K, Walsh A, Verstuyft JG, Rubin EM, Breslow JL (1992) Severe hypercholesterolemia and atherosclerosis in apolipoprotein E-deficient mice created by homologous recombination in ES cells. *Cell* 71(2): 343–353. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0092-8674\(92\)90362-g](https://doi.org/10.1016/0092-8674(92)90362-g) [PubMed]
- Polonikov A, Bykanova M, Ponomarenko I, Sirotina S, Bocharova A, Vagaytseva K, Stepanov V, Churnosov M, Bushueva O, Solodilova M, Shvetsov Y, Ivanov V (2017) The contribution of CYP2C gene subfamily involved in epoxygenase pathway of arachidonic acids metabolism to hypertension susceptibility in Russian population. *Clinical and Experimental Hypertension* 39(4): 306–311. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10641963.2016.1246562> [PubMed]
- Prospective Studies Collaboration, Lewington S, Whitlock G, Clarke R, Sherliker P, Emberson J, Halsey J, Qizilbash N, Peto R, Collins R (2007) Blood cholesterol and vascular mortality by age, sex, and blood pressure: a meta-analysis of individual data from 61 prospective studies with 55,000 vascular deaths. *Lancet* 370(9602): 1829–1839. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(07\)61778-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(07)61778-4) [PubMed]
- Pytela R, Pierschbacher MD, Ginsberg MH, Plow EF, Ruoslahti E (1986) Platelet membrane glycoprotein IIb/IIIa: member of a family of Arg-Gly-Asp-specific adhesion receptors. *Science* 231(4745): 1559–1562. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.2420006> [PubMed]
- Qin C, Zhou S, Xiao Y, Chen L (2014) Erythropoietin enhances mitochondrial biogenesis in cardiomyocytes exposed to chronic hypoxia through Akt/eNOS signalling pathway. *Cell Biology International* 38(3): 335–342. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbin.10205> [PubMed]
- Quintero M, Colombo SL, Godfrey A, Moncada S (2006) Mitochondria as signaling organelles in the vascular endothelium. *Proceeding of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 103(14): 5379–5384. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0601026103> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Rayner KJ, Sheedy FJ, Esau CC, Hussain FN, Temel RE, Parathath S, van Gils JM, Rayner AJ, Chang AN, Suarez Y, Fernandez-Hernando C, Fisher EA, Moore KJ (2011) Antagonism of miR-33 in

- mice promotes reverse cholesterol transport and regression of atherosclerosis. *The Journal of Clinical Investigation* 121(7): 2921–2931. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI57275> [PubMed] [PMC]
- Ridker PM, MacFadyen JG, Everett BM, Libby P, Thuren T, Glynn RJ, CANTOS Trial Group (2018) Relationship of C-reactive protein reduction to cardiovascular event reduction following treatment with canakinumab: a secondary analysis from the CANTOS randomised controlled trial. *Lancet* 391(10118): 319–328. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)32814-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)32814-3) [PubMed]
 - Rogacev KS, Cremers B, Zawada AM, Seiler S, Binder N, Ege P, Große-Dunker G, Heisel I, Hornof F, Jeken J, Rebling NM, Ulrich C, Scheller B, Böhm M, Fliser D, Heine GH (2012) CD14⁺⁺CD16⁺ monocytes independently predict cardiovascular events: a cohort study of 951 patients referred for elective coronary angiography. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology* 60(16): 1512–1520. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2012.07.019> [PubMed]
 - Rosenblat M, Aviram M (2002) Oxysterol-induced activation of macrophage NADPH-oxidase enhances cell-mediated oxidation of LDL in the atherosclerotic apolipoprotein E deficient mouse: inhibitory role for vitamin E. *Atherosclerosis* 160(1): 69–80. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9150\(01\)00563-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9150(01)00563-9) [PubMed]
 - Rosenblat M, Coleman R, Aviram M (2002) Increased macrophage glutathione content reduces cell-mediated oxidation of LDL and atherosclerosis in apolipoprotein E-deficient mice. *Atherosclerosis* 163(1): 17–28. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9150\(01\)00744-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9150(01)00744-4) [PubMed]
 - Schwartz EA, Reaven PD (2012) Lipolysis of triglyceride-rich lipoproteins, vascular inflammation, and atherosclerosis. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta* 1821(5): 858–866. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bba-lip.2011.09.021> [PubMed]
 - Shenouda SM, Widlansky ME, Chen K, Xu G, Holbrook M, Tabit CE (2011) Altered mitochondrial dynamics contributes to endothelial dysfunction in diabetes mellitus. *Circulation* 124(4): 444–453. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.110.014506> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Sheu JR, Yen MH, Peng IC, Chang MC, Huang TF (1995) Triflavin, an Arg-Gly-Asp-containing peptide, prevents platelet plug formation in vivo by blocking glycoprotein IIb/IIIa complex. *European Journal of Pharmacology* 294(1): 231–238. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2999\(95\)00530-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2999(95)00530-7) [PubMed]
 - Shevchenko KV, Nagaev IY, Andreeva LA, Shevchenko VP, Myasoedov NF (2019) Stability of prolin-containing peptides in biological media. *Biochemistry (Moscow), Supplement Series B: Biomedical Chemistry* 65(3): 180–201. <https://doi.org/10.18097/PBMC20196503180> [PubMed]
 - Song Y, Stampfer MJ, Liu S (2004) Meta-analysis: apolipoprotein E genotypes and risk for coronary heart disease. *Annals of Internal Medicine* 141(2): 137–147. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-141-2-200407200-00013> [PubMed]
 - Swartjes M, Velzen M, Niesters M (2014) ARA 290, a peptide derived from the tertiary structure of erythropoietin, produces long-term relief of neuropathic pain coupled with suppression of the spinal microglia response. *Molecular Pain* 10: 1744–1769. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2F174480691013> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Tall AR, Yvan-Charvet L (2015) Cholesterol, inflammation and innate immunity. *Nature Reviews. Immunology* 15(2): 104–116. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nri3793> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Tang C, Liu Y, Kessler PS, Vaughan AM, Oram JF (2009) The macrophage cholesterol exporter ABCA1 functions as an anti-inflammatory receptor. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry* 284(47): 32336–32343. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M109.047472> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Torzewski M, Lackner KJ (2006) Initiation and progression of atherosclerosis – enzymatic or oxidative modification of low-density lipoprotein?. *Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine* 44(12): 1389–1394. <https://doi.org/10.1515/CCLM.2006.259> [PubMed]
 - Torzewski M, Suriyaphol P, Paprotka K, Spath L, Ochsenhirt V, Schmitt A, Han SR, Husmann M, Gerl VB, Bhakdi S, Lackner KJ (2004) Enzymatic modification of low-density lipoprotein in the arterial wall: a new role for plasmin and matrix metalloproteinases in atherogenesis. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology* 24(11): 2130–2136. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.ATV.0000144016.85221.66> [PubMed]
 - Ungvari Z, Labinskyy N, Gupte S, Chander PN, Edwards JG, Csiszar A (2008) Dysregulation of mitochondrial biogenesis in vascular endothelial and smooth muscle cells of aged rats. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart Circulatory Physiology* 294(5): 2121–2128. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00012.2008> [PubMed]
 - Utermann G, Hardewig A, Zimmer F (1984) Apolipoprotein E phenotypes in patients with myocardial infarction. *Human Genetics* 65(3): 237–241. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00286509> [PubMed]
 - Vickers KC, Landstreet SR, Levin MG, Shoucri BM, Toth CL, Taylor RC, Palmisano BT, Tabet F, Cui HL, Rye KA, Sethupathy P, Remaley AT (2014) MicroRNA-223 coordinates cholesterol homeostasis. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 111: 14518–14523. [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Wang XQ, Panousis CG, Alfaro ML, Evans GF, Zuckerman SH (2002) Interferon-gamma-mediated downregulation of cholesterol efflux and ABC1 expression is by the Stat1 pathway. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology* 22(5): e5–e9. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.atv.0000018287.03856.dd> [PubMed]
 - Wang Z, Zhang S, Jin H, Wang W, Huo J, Zhou L, Wang Y, Feng F, Zhang L (2011) Angiotensin-I-converting enzyme inhibitory peptides: Chemical feature based pharmacophore generation. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 46(8): 3428–3433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2011.05.007> [PubMed]
 - Wu D, Sharan C, Yang H, Goodwin JS, Zhou L, Grabowski GA, Du H, Guo Z (2007) Apolipoprotein E-deficient lipoproteins induce foam cell formation by downregulation of lysosomal hydrolases in macrophages. *Journal of Lipid Research* 48(12): 2571–2578. <https://doi.org/10.1194/jlr.M700217-JLR200> [PubMed]
 - Yancey PG, Jerome WG, Yu H, Griffin EE, Cox BE, Babaev VR, Fazio S, Linton MF (2007a) Severely altered cholesterol homeostasis in macrophages lacking apoE and SR-BI. *Journal of Lipid Research* 48(5): 1140–1149. <https://doi.org/10.1194/jlr.M600539-JLR200> [PubMed]
 - Yancey PG, Yu H, Linton MF, Fazio S (2007b) A pathway-dependent on apoE, ApoAI, and ABCA1 determines formation of buoyant high-density lipoprotein by macrophage foam cells. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular biology* 27(5): 1123–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1161/ATVBAHA.107.139592> [PubMed]
 - Yang C, Zhang C, Jia J, Wang L, Zhang W, Li J, Xu M, Rong R, Zhu T (2019) Cyclic helix B peptide ameliorates acute myocardial infarction in mice by inhibiting apoptosis and inflammatory responses. *Cell Death Discovery* 5(1): 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41420-019-0161-y> [PubMed] [PMC]
 - Ye D, Lammers B, Zhao Y, Meurs I, Van Berkel TJ, Van Eck M (2011) ATP-binding cassette transporters A1 and G1, HDL metabo-

- lism, cholesterol efflux, and inflammation: important targets for the treatment of atherosclerosis. *Current Drug Targets* 12(5): 647–660. <https://doi.org/10.2174/138945011795378522> [PubMed]
- Younis N, Sharma R, Soran H, Charlton-Menys V, Elseweidy M, Durrington PN (2008) Glycation as an atherogenic modification of LDL. *Current Opinion in Lipidology* 19(4): 378–384. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MOL.0b013e328306a057> [PubMed]
 - Yu S, Duan RS, Chen Z, Quezada HC, Bao L, Nennesmo I, Zhu SW, Winblad B, Ljunggren HG, Zhu J (2004) Increased susceptibility to experimental autoimmune neuritis after upregulation of the autoreactive T cell response to peripheral myelin antigen in apolipoprotein E-deficient mice. *Journal of Neuropathology and Experimental Neurology* 63(2): 120–128. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnen/63.2.120> [PubMed]
 - Zanotti I, Pedrelli M, Poti F, Stomeo G, Gomaschi M, Calabresi L, Bernini F (2011) Macrophage, but not systemic, apolipoprotein E is necessary for macrophage reverse cholesterol transport in vivo. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology* 31(1): 74–80. <https://doi.org/10.1161/ATVBAHA.110.213892> [PubMed]
 - Zárate A, Manuel-Apolinar L, Basurto L, De la Chesnaye E, Saldívar I (2016) Colesterol y aterosclerosis. Consideraciones históricas y tratamiento [Cholesterol and atherosclerosis. Historical considerations and treatment]. *Archivos de Cardiología de México* 86(2): 163–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acmx.2015.12.002> [PubMed]
 - Zhang C, Yang C, Zhu T (2017) From erythropoietin to its peptide derivatives: smaller but stronger. *Current Protein and Peptide Science* 18(12): 1191–1194. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1389203717666160909130006> [PubMed]
 - Zhang SH, Reddick RL, Piedrahita JA, Maeda N (1992) Spontaneous hypercholesterolemia and arterial lesions in mice lacking apolipoprotein E. *Science* 258(5081): 468–471. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1411543> [PubMed] [Full Text]
 - Zhou R, Yazdi AS, Menu P, Tschopp J (2011a) A role for mitochondria in NLRP3 inflammasome activation. *Nature* 469(7329): 221–225. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature09663> [PubMed]
 - Zhou S, Chen HZ, Wan YZ, Zhang QJ, Wei YS, Huang S (2011b) Repression of P66Shc expression by SIRT1 contributes to the prevention of hyperglycemia-induced endothelial dysfunction. *Circulation Research* 109(6): 639–648. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.111.243592> [PubMed]
 - Zhuang G, Meng C, Guo X, Cheruku PS, Shi L, Xu H, Li H, Wang G, Evans AR, Safe S, Wu C, Zhou B (2012) A novel regulator of macrophage activation: miR-223 in obesity-associated adipose tissue inflammation. *Circulation* 125: 2892–2903. [PubMed]

Author contributions

All authors contributed equally to the writing of the submitted review.

- **Veronika S. Belyaeva**, Postgraduate student, e-mail: nika.believa@yandex.ru, **ORCID ID 0000-0003-2941-0241**. The author participated in the article writing.
- **Yulia V. Stepenko**, Postgraduate student, e-mail: julia.v.stepenko@gmail.com, **ORCID ID 0000-0002-7414-7326**. The author participated in the article writing.
- **Igor I. Lyubimov**, Candidate of Biological Sciences, General Manager, e-mail: lyubimov@gurus.bio, **ORCID ID 0000-0002-0057-8537**. The author consulted on the idea of the review, analysis of literature data and conclusions.
- **Alexandr L. Kulikov**, Researcher, e-mail: alex-3031@yandex.ru, **ORCID ID 0000-0001-6422-0377**. The author was engaged in writing the article and formalization of the references.
- **Alesia A. Tietze**, Senior Lecturer (Assistant Professor) in Medicinal Chemistry with focus on total synthesis of bioactive peptides, e-mail: a.tietze@tietze-lab.com, **ORCID ID 0000-0002-9281-548X**. The author consulted on the idea of the review and analyzed the literature data.
- **Indira S. Kochkarova**, Junior researcher, Research Institute of Pharmacology of Living Systems, e-mail: kochkarova@bsu.edu.ru. The author analyzed the literature data.
- **Olga V. Martynova**, Researcher, e-mail: m.olga91@mail.ru, **ORCID ID 0000-0003-4104-4993**. The author analyzed the literature data.
- **Olga N. Pokopeyko**, Undergraduate student, Moscow, Russia, e-mail: pokopejko@yandex.ru. The author analyzed the literature data.
- **Liliya A. Krupen’kina**, Assistant Professor, e-mail: crupenkina@lyandex.ru, **ORCID ID 0000-0003-3299-5877**. The author analyzed the literature data.
- **Andrey S. Nagikh**, Postgraduate student, e-mail: nagikhandrew@gmail.com, **ORCID ID 0000-0002-2505-4422**. The author analyzed the literature data.

- **Vladimir M. Pokrovskiy**, 5-year student, e-mail: vmokrovsky@yandex.ru, **ORCID ID 0000-0003-3138-2075**. The author analyzed the literature data.
- **Evgeniy A. Patrakhanov**, 5-year student, e-mail: pateval7@gmail.com, **ORCID ID 0000-0002-8415-4562**. The author analyzed the literature data.
- **Anastasia V. Belashova**, 5-year student, e-mail: belashova_av@mail.ru, **ORCID ID 0000-0001-9737-6378**. The author participated in the article writing.
- **Petr R. Lebedev**, 5-year student, e-mail: Artkelt98@yandex.ru, **ORCID ID 0000-0001-9102-3360**. The author analyzed the literature data.
- **Anastasia V. Gureeva**, 3-year student, e-mail: nastasyi.207@gmail.com, **ORCID ID 0000-0003-1719-7316**. The author participated in the article writing.